

Counselling Needs of Out-Of-School-Adolescents in Southwest, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study examined counselling needs of out-of-school-adolescents in Southwest, Nigeria. The study specifically assessed the counselling needs of out-of-school-adolescents; and determined the sex and location difference in counselling needs of out-of-school-adolescents. Descriptive survey research design was used in the study. The population of the study consisted of out-of-school-adolescents in Southwest Nigeria. The study sample consisted of 1458 out-of-school-adolescents in Southwest Nigeria. The sample was selected using multistage sampling procedure. Questionnaire on Counselling Needs (QCN) was designed by the researchers to collect the data needed for the study. The instrument was subjected to face and content validity by experts in Guidance and Counselling, and Tests and Measurement. The reliability of this instrument was subjected to test re-test method and the reliability coefficient was 0.802. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyse the collected and collated data. The study reveals that out-of-school-adolescents have highest preference for counselling need on achievement motivation, closely followed by altruism and religious faith while the least preference was counselling need on nationalism. The study also concludes that counselling needs of out-of-school-adolescents in Southwest Nigeria was not significantly differentiated by sex and location. It was recommended among others that Counselling Psychologists should focus their attention on issues arising from counselling needs of out-of-school-adolescents.

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Introduction

Adolescents, of school age being out of school appears a serious issue because it appears it is a violation of their human right to education and a life not free from violence, danger, and untimely death. UNESCO (2018) observed that Nigeria, accounts for almost a fifth of world's out-of-school-adolescents. It appears convincing to observe that, when adolescents are in school, well monitored, and prevented from association with peer groups of questionable character and are made to study in a conducive learning environment, they grow up being properly oriented towards being responsible citizen of a nation. Education therefore, appears to be a strong social experience that promotes consistent moral and individual growth. To this, Elizabeth (2011) succinctly submits that education is fundamental to human development and growth. According to her, the human minds make possible all development and achievement, from health advances and agricultural innovation to efficient public administration and private sector growth. For countries to reap the benefits of human development fully, they need to unleash the potentials of the human mind through education, since growth, development, and poverty reduction depends on the knowledge and skills that people acquire as we transform from the call for "Education for All" to "Learning for All".

It is pertinent to note that the United Nations (2019) recently released Nigeria's estimated population as at 12th of May, 2019 which is to be 200,209,652, and with a mean age of 17.5 years (adolescent's age bracket) population in Nigeria. The report also shows that adolescents and children not in school have been estimated to have increased from 10.5 million in 2015 to 13.2 million in 2019, a figure estimate released in collaboration with Nigeria's National Demographic Health Survey (NDHS, 2015). This figure according to UNESCO Fact Sheet number 48 (2018) accounts for more than one in every five Nigerian out-of-school-adolescents estimated to be 45 per-cent of the total number of out-of-school-adolescents in West Africa sub-region.

A more specific and statistically relevant data to this study is that of the Southwest geo-political zone data published by the Multiple Indicator Cluster Survey (MICS), 2016/2017 conducted by Nigeria Bureau of Statistics (NBS) and United Nations International Children Education Fund (UNICEF) (2019) showing Southwest States data of out-of-school-adolescents as follows: Lagos State has 229,264 out-of-school adolescents, Ekiti State has 99,778, Ondo State has 113,746, Oyo State has 463,280, Ogun State has 158,797, and Osun State has 260,522. The sum total being 1,325,387, out-of-school adolescents in southwest geopolitical zone of Nigeria (Ogunyemi in Punch, 28th June, 2019).

Counselling in this study is described as the process of helping an individual or group of out-of-school-adolescent(s) to gain self-understanding in order to congruently be themselves as they come face to face in professional relationship with a trained Counsellor (Olofintoye, Falana & Alao, 2016). The need for out-of-school-adolescents to identify and understand their emotions, negative thinking, illogical reasoning, doubts, conflicts, also appear a major counselling needs. There is also the need to assess their abilities, interest, thinking, and capabilities to ensure their personal, social, and psychological adjustment through professional counselling intervention. The counselling process between the counsellor and the counsellee may also help the client make his own reasonable decisions and choices, that will ensure resolving his own cognitive errors, negative thinking, confusion, correct his behaviour disorder, and to evolve a new psychologically congruent behaviour that will overcome distress and despair. Counselling needs of out-of-school-adolescents will be determined by a identifying a measure of the traits they possess on the variables of nationalism, altruism, religious faith, achievement motivation. In view of the above, the study

examined counselling needs of out-of-school-adolescents in Southwest, Nigeria. The study specifically:

1. assessed the counselling needs of out-of-school-adolescents;
2. determined the sex difference in counselling needs of out-of-school-adolescents; and
3. examined the location difference in counselling needs of out-of-school-adolescents.

Research Question

This research question was raised for this study;

1. What are the counselling needs of out-of-school-adolescents?

Research Hypotheses

The null hypotheses below were postulated for this study;

1. Sex will not significantly determine the counselling needs of out-of-school-adolescents.
2. The counselling needs of out-of-school-adolescents will not be significantly determined by their location.

Methodology

Descriptive survey research design was used in the study. The design presents a description of events as they are, and facilitates easy collection of factual information about the research problem. The population of the study consisted of out-of-school-adolescents in Southwest Nigeria. The total number of out-of-school-adolescents as at this time of study was 1,325,387 (United Nations International Children Education Fund Global Initiative, Nigeria, 2019). The study sample consisted of 1458 out-of-school-adolescents in Southwest Nigeria. The sample was selected using multistage sampling procedure. The first stage involved simple random sampling of three states out of six states in the Southwest Nigeria. The second stage involved the use of purposive sampling technique to select five Local Government Areas each from the three selected states making a total of fifteen Local Government Areas. However, respondents were selected based on proportional sampling technique because there were variations in the number of out-of-school-adolescents at the various local Governments.

Questionnaire on Counselling Needs (QCN) was designed by the researchers to collect the data needed for the study. The instrument consisted of two sections namely Sections A and B. Section A sought for the personal data of the respondents on certain variables such as gender and location while Section B contained 24 items that measured counselling needs in the area of nationalism, altruism, religious faith and achievement motivation. A four point Likert-type scale of strongly agree, agree, disagree, and strongly disagree was adopted in Section B. The high point indicates high counselling needs, while the low point indicates low counselling needs of out-of-school-adolescent.

The instrument was subjected to face and content validity by experts in Guidance and Counselling, and Tests and Measurement. The reliability of this instrument was subjected to test re-test method. The scores obtained from the two separate administration of the test were correlated using Pearson Product Moment Correlation and it yielded coefficient value of 0.802. The data of the study were collected and collated by the researcher after the administration of the questionnaire in three selected states of Southwest, Nigeria. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyse the collated data.

Results

Research Question 1: What are the counselling needs of out-of-school-adolescents?

In answering this question, data on counselling needs of out-of-school-adolescents were collected from the responses of the respondents to items under Section C of QCN (item 1

- 24) in the questionnaire. The data were collated and analysed using descriptive statistics such as frequency counts and mean.

Table 1: Mean Scores of counselling needs of out-of-school-adolescents

S/N	ITEMS	Total Mean	Average Mean	Rank
1	Nationalism	11.08	1.85	4 th
2	Altruism	12.83	2.14	2 nd
3	Religious Faith	12.30	2.05	3 rd
4	Achievement Motivation	15.47	2.58	1 st

Figure i: Bar chart showing counselling needs of out-of-school-adolescents

Table 1 and figure i showed the counselling needs of out-of-school-adolescents. The result indicated that the average mean mark of nationalism counselling need is ($\bar{x} = 1.85$), altruism counselling need ($\bar{x} = 2.14$), religious faith counselling need ($\bar{x} = 2.05$) and achievement motivation counselling need ($\bar{x} = 2.58$). It is deduced from the above that out-of-school-adolescents have highest preference for counselling need on achievement motivation, closely followed by altruism and religious faith while the least preference was counselling need on nationalism.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: Sex will not significantly determine the counselling needs of out-of-school-adolescents.

In order to test the hypothesis, data on counselling needs were collected from the responses of the respondents to items under Section B of QCN (item 1 - 24) in the

questionnaire. t-test was used to compute difference in counselling needs between male and female out-of-school-adolescents. The result is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: t-test Analysis for difference in counselling needs of out-of-school-adolescents based on their sex

Variations	N	Mean	SD	df	t _{cal}	P
Male	976	51.63	5.88	1456	0.441	0.659
Female	482	51.78	6.30			

P>0.05

Table 18 shows that the t-cal value of 0.441 was not significant because the P value (0.659) > 0.05. This implies that null hypothesis was not rejected. Hence, sex does not significantly determine the counselling needs of out-of-school-adolescents.

Hypothesis 2: The counselling needs of out-of-school-adolescents will not be significantly determined by their location.

In order to test the hypothesis, data on counselling needs were collected from the responses of the respondents to items under Section B of QCN (item 1 – 24) in the questionnaire. t-test was used to compute difference in counselling needs between rural and urban out-of-school-adolescents. The result is presented in Table 3.

Table 3: t-test Analysis for difference in counselling needs of out-of-school-adolescents based on their location

Variations	N	Mean	SD	df	t _{cal}	P
Rural	846	51.85	6.15	1456	1.310	0.191
Urban	612	51.44	5.83			

P>0.05

Table 3 shows that the t-cal value of 1.310 was not significant because the P value (0.191) > 0.05. This implies that null hypothesis was not rejected. Hence, the counselling needs of out-of-school-adolescents was not significantly determined by their location.

Discussion

The study reveals that out-of-school-adolescents have highest preference for counselling need on achievement motivation, closely followed by altruism and religious faith while the least preference was counselling need on nationalism. In support of this finding, Okoiye and Adebisi (2015) reported a situation assessment of out-of-school-adolescents need for counselling intervention on achievement motivation. Elena, Joana, and Mait (2019) also concluded that out-of-school-adolescents have highest preference for counselling need on achievement motivation. Pushpalatha and Sasikala (2015) see guidance and counselling of adolescents as giving them orientation on how to face the ever changing challenges in today's fast-moving technological world, and pointed out counselling goals of out-of-school-adolescents as that of facilitating behavioural change, enhancing coping skills, promoting decision making, improving relationship, and facilitating client's potentials.

The study revealed that sex does not significantly determine the counselling needs of out-of-school-adolescents. This implies that the male and female out-of-school-adolescents have the same counselling needs. In consonance with the findings of this study, Viyalaxmi and Varsh (2014) revealed that there were no significant differences between the responses of male and female adolescents on counselling needs.

The study also reveals that the counselling needs of out-of-school-adolescents were not significantly determined by their location. In consonance with this finding, Okoiye and

Adebisi (2015) found that out-of-school-adolescents in rural and urban areas exhibit similar counselling needs.

Conclusion

The study concludes that out-of-school-adolescents need more counselling in the area of achievement motivation, closely followed by altruism and religious faith. The least counselling need of out-of-school adolescent is on nationalism. The study also concludes that counselling needs of out-of-school-adolescents in Southwest Nigeria was not significantly differentiated by sex and location.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that:

1. The government should designate counselling centres out of school setting that can handle the counselling needs of out-of-school adolescents.
2. Counsellors should understand the counselling needs of their needy out-of-school-adolescents when they come face to face on a one on one counselling session
3. Counselling Psychologists should focus their attention on issues arising from counselling needs of out-of-school-adolescents.

References

- Elena, B.; Joana, J. & Mait, G. (2019). Child and adolescent depression: A review of theories, evaluation instrument, prevention programmes and treatment. Retrieved February 23rd 2021 from <https://doi.org/103389/fpsyg-2019.00543>.
- Elizabeth, K. (2011). Education is fundamental to development and growth. Retrieved July 5th 2021 from <https://www.worldbank-fact-sheet.com>
- National Demographic and Health Survey (2015). Adolescents and youths retrieved 10th October, 2020 from unfpa.org/data/adolescents-youths
- Ogunyemi, S. (2019, June 28). Inter-generational illiteracy. Nigerian Punch p8.
- Okoie, O. E. & Adebisi, K. F. (2015). Effect of cognitive and rational emotive behaviour therapies on drug abuse of senior secondary school students in Ibadan. *British Journal of Marketing studies*, 3(6) 41 – 52.
- Olofintoye, T.T., Falana, B.A. & Alao, D.D. (2016). Resolving youth restiveness in Nigeria through entrepreneurial counselling. *Ekiti State University Journal of Education*, 6(1), 78 -89
- Pushpalatha, C. & Sasikala, S. (2015). Counselling Needs among Adolescents students. *Indian Journal of Applied Research*, 5(12), 107 – 112.
- UNESCO (2018). One in five children, adolescents and youths is out of school. Source: (Fact sheet number 48 UIS/FS/2018/ED/48. Retrieved March 17th 2021 From <https://www.uis.unesco.org>
- United Nation Development Programme Bureau (2019). Nigeria's Population as at 12th May, 2019. Retrieved 25th June, 2021 <http://www.n3cb.gov.ph/ru12/DEFINE/Def-Edu.HTN>.
- Vijyalaxmi, C. & Varsha, J. (2014). Sex difference in counselling needs: A study among adolescents. *Indian Journal of Psychology and Education*. 4(1), 40 -42.

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